

sible electrode reaction of Ni(II) remains the same under both the two conditions of pH. Under the two conditions of pH the rate constant, k_p^n , decreases with increasing concentrations of tryptophan. It follows from this that the irreversible electrode reaction of Ni(II) is rendered increasingly more irreversible as the concentration of tryptophan is increased. The parameter αn_a also decreases with increasing concentrations of tryptophan under different conditions of pH. The polarographic reduction of Ni(II) is a well-established 2-electron reduction process and therefore n_a , the number of electrons involved in the rate determining step, can either be 1 or 2. Since the decrease in αn_a values is indiscrete and at no stage the two consecutive values differ by a factor of 2, the possibility of a decrease in the value of the product αn_a due to a change in n_a may be ruled out. Thus it can be safely concluded that it is α which is decreasing. α , the transfer coefficient, signifies¹³ the fraction of the applied voltage which favours the cathodic reaction, $\text{Ni}^{2+} + 2e \rightarrow \text{Ni}$. A decrease in the value of α thus implies that the transfer of electron/electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words, the electrode reaction of Ni(II) is rendered increasingly more irreversible as the concentration of L-tryptophan is increased. Thus, the variations in the values of both the kinetic parameters point to the same conclusion.

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Reactivity of Indian Rock Phosphates in Presence of Oxidative Degradation Products of Coal

D. N. PATHAK

Department of Chemistry, Regional Institute of Technology,
Jamshedpur-831 014

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THE oxidative degradation products of coal, obtained by the action of potassium permanganate in presence of rock phosphate in aqueous solution, increase the reactivity of rock phosphates

resulting in the dissolution of more phosphatic content in water.

A variety of oxidizing agents, mostly in acidic medium, were used in the past for controlled low temperature degradation of coal¹. Later, oxidation of coal in alkaline medium using potassium permanganate was studied in detail²⁻⁶. The different parameters upon which the oxidative degradation of coal in alkaline medium is dependent was investigated very recently by Banerji⁷. Contradictory reports^{8,9} on the reactivity of Indian rock phosphates posed a great problem of its utility to chemists all over the world. The work of Johnston¹⁰ on the dissolution of insoluble phosphate in aqueous solutions of organic acids prompted the author to design the present investigation for determining the extent of reactivity by water soluble organic acids produced in the oxidative degradation of coal by potassium permanganate in presence of rock phosphates.

Experimental

Rock phosphates from Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and Bihar, obtained through Geological Survey of India, were powdered, sieved (100 mesh, B.S.S.) and analysed according to the procedure of Washington¹¹.

A number of stoppered conical flasks were taken and 1g finely powdered sample of each rock phosphate, 0.5 g coal (dmf, 36 mesh BSS, C=80%) and 100 ml 0.1 N KMnO₄ solution were added in each of the flasks. The flasks with their contents were kept agitated in a mechanical shaker at room temperature (27°). After definite intervals of time the solution of each flask was allowed to stand for some time, filtered and washed with water through a sintered glass crucible. Aliquot portions were utilized for determining P₂O₅ and for measuring the extent of oxidative degradation¹². A blank (mineral + water) estimation was also simultaneously carried out.

Phosphate was estimated volumetrically after precipitating with ammonium molybdate solution.

In order to measure the extent of oxidative degradation, a suitable portion of the aliquot was treated with solid KI and acidified with conc. HCl. The liberated iodine was titrated against a standard thiosulphate solution using starch as an indicator. Permanganate consumed by coal in different time intervals was calculated from the titre values.

Results and Discussion

The analysis (Table 1) shows that the rock phosphates contain varying amounts of P₂O₅ (12 to 30%), magnesium and iron, suitable for healthy plant growth. It is interesting to record that all the rock phosphates are alkaline in aqueous solutions.

The experimental results (Tables 2 and 3) show that the release of phosphate from rock phosphates by water is not much. However, with water soluble aromatic polycarboxylic acids, produced as a result of degradation of coal by oxidizing action of alkaline

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF VARIOUS ROCK PHOSPHATES

Ingredients %	RP	MNP	MPS	MGP	MVLP	MRP	I(B)RP
Insoluble material	5.60	7.56	26.05	5.90	17.26	3.24	24.14
Al ₂ O ₃	1.42	23.05	23.92	25.51	33.90	31.26	18.96
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.28	0.25	0.24	0.25	0.32	0.96	12.17
CaO	44.98	32.15	17.00	16.45	15.50	11.38	9.81
MgO	0.08	0.09	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.35
P ₂ O ₅	27.18	15.46	10.34	30.17	11.97	30.72	15.60

RP - Rajasthan Phosphate,
 MNP - Mussorie Nodular Phosphorite,
 MPS - Mussorie Phosphorite Shale,
 MGP - Mussorie Granular Phosphorite,
 MRP - Mussorie Rock Phosphate,
 I(B)RP - Itagarh (Bihar) Rock Phosphate.

TABLE 2—RELEASE OF P₂O₅ (G/L) FROM ROCK PHOSPHATES IN WATER AFTER 24 HR AT 27°

Period After 24 hr	RP	MNP	MPS	MGP	MVLP	MRP	I(B)RP
	0.0052	0.0045	0.0012	0.0040	0.0009	0.0033	0.0025

TABLE 3—RELEASE OF P₂O₅ (G/L) FROM ROCK PHOSPHATES IN THE OXIDATIVE DEGRADATION OF COAL AT 27°

Period After	RP	MNP	MPS	MGP	MVLP	MRP	I(B)RP
2 hr	0.0110	0.0076	0.0023	0.0071	0.0017	0.0063	0.0048
4 hr	0.0137	0.0099	0.0035	0.0090	0.0030	0.0077	0.0060
6 hr	0.0163	0.0115	0.0047	0.0105	0.0043	0.0091	0.0077
8 hr	0.0223	0.0158	0.0083	0.0145	0.0075	0.0128	0.0115

permanganate in aqueous solution, the release increases to a marked extent. The colour of permanganate changes gradually from brown to colourless at the end of 8 hr showing thereby that the reduction occurs in a step wise process.

According to Banerjee⁷, for a typical low rank coal (C=79.2%), the optimum volume and concentration of permanganate solution for complete oxidation, i.e. when no coal particle is left over as residue, are 20.2 × 10⁻³ mole/litre and 225 ml/g of coal (dmf), respectively. The release of P₂O₅ from various rock phosphates shows a progressive increase with lapse of time. This is because of the fact that degradation of coal, which continues upto above 8 hr, produces more and more water soluble organic acids which help in the dissolution of increasing amount of phosphatic content.

During the course of this investigation it was noticed that after a few hours the solutions in all the systems became colloidal. This is because of the formation of finely divided hydrated manganese oxide as a result of the reduction of permanganate and intermediate formation of humic acid on account of degradation of coal. With lapse of time, further degradation of humic acid into benzene carboxylic acids occurs and the solution becomes clear.

Thus, the reactivity of Indian rock phosphates increases to an appreciable extent by the permanganate oxidation of coal.

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Triazolo [3, 4-b] [1, 3, 4] thiadiazoles

H. K. GAKHAR, ANJU JAIN

and

SHASHI BHUSHAN GUPTA

Chemistry Department, Panjab University,
 Chandigarh-160 014

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LITERATURE records¹⁻³ the synthesis of some *s*-triazolo [3, 4-b] [1, 3, 4] thiadiazoles. One such synthesis is by George *et al*⁴ but the yields recorded are low. We report here the synthesis of some new *s*-triazolo [3, 4-b] [1, 3, 4] thiadiazoles by the modification of the above procedure, where very good yields of the compounds were obtained.

The compounds have been prepared by the condensation of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-*s*-triazole (I) with various aldehydes in the presence of sodium acetate. The structure (III) for these compounds finds support from analysis and pmr data. PMR* of IIIa in CDCl₃-DMSO-d₆ showed a doublet (3H) at 2.37 assignable to three methyl protons at position 6. It also showed a singlet (3H) at 3.20 assignable to three protons of methyl group at position 3. The signals due to one proton attached to C₅ and one proton attached to nitrogen overlapped and gave a broad signal at 5.20.

*Chemical shifts in δ (ppm).